

CARBONATE CONTENT OF MEADOW-ALLUVIAL AND TAKYR-LIKE MEADOW SOILS UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF DESERTIFICATION

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Abstract: The article presents information on the carbonate content and calcium and magnesium carbonates in the carbonate content of the soils distributed on the right and left banks of the Lower Amudarya.

Key words: meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow, common carbonates, calcium carbonate, magnesium carbonate, dolomite.

Introduction: As a result of the negative impact of human activity, significant changes in the environment are observed in many regions of our planet. One of them is global climate change, various natural disasters, which are felt in all latitudes of the planet. As a result, the areas covered with natural forests are decreasing, various negative processes in the atmosphere, water and lithosphere are increasing.

Determination of carbonates in soils is very important, where high amounts of calcium and magnesium carbonates increase the alkalinity of the soil reaction (pH) and significantly reduce the mobility of nutrients, in which the amount of mobile nutrients that can be absorbed by plants in the soil can fall to a deficit level, and after the depletion of nutrients in the soil, has a negative effect on the growth and development of plants.

Research object and methods: Old and newly irrigated meadow-alluvial and takyr-like meadow soils, widespread in Chimboy and Shumanay districts on the right and left banks of the Lower Amudarya, are the object of research.

Genetic-geographical, lithological-geomorphological, comparative, profile and chemical-analytical methods were used in the research. Soil research is carried out according to "Manual for conducting soil research and drawing up soil maps for the state land cadastre" [1], chemical analysis of soil samples are carried out according to "Agrokhimicheskie metody issledovaniya pochv i

rastenyi", UzPITI [2], "Rukovodstvo po khimicheskomu analizu pochv" and the manuals of E.V. Arinushkina [3].

The obtained results and their analysis: The acidimetric method was used to determine the amount of carbonate in the soils distributed on the right and left banks of the Lower Amudarya. Determination of carbon content of soils is based on their decomposition with 0.02 N hydrochloric acid.

An increase in the amount of CO₂ in the soil solution causes an increase in the solubility of CaCO₃, and calcium carbonate partially turns into bicarbonate. As a result of the formation of HCO₃ ions in the soil, the alkalinity of the soil increases and causes a sharp increase in the pH indicator, that is, the formation of soda (NaCO₃) [4].

Table 1.

The amount of carbonates in the soils on the right and left banks of the Lower Amudarya, %.

Layer depth, cm	CO ₂	CaCO ₃	MgCO ₃
	%		
1. Chimboy district B-2 Irrigated takyr-like meadow. The modern delta of Amudarya, consisting of alluvial deposits			
0-28	9,8	8,40	1,241
28-49	10,0	8,60	1,219
49-70	10,1	7,70	1,095
70-93	8,1	6,50	1,584
93-112	8,6	7,10	0,292
112-160	9,3	7,40	1,022
2. Chimboy district B-4 Irrigated takyr-like meadow. The modern delta of Amudarya, consisting of alluvial deposits			
0-24	8,3	7,70	0,584
24-49	8,5	7,50	0,949
49-61	10,3	8,90	1,387
61-75	10,7	9,70	0,949
75-100	10,1	9,20	0,876
100-131	8,1	7,50	0,511
131-200	7,6	7,40	0,292
3. Shumanay district Sh-5 Irrigated meadow-alluvial. Delta of Amudarya formed from layered alluvial deposits			
0-43	9,8	7,98	0,365
43-65	10,4	8,12	1,022

65-87	9,7	7,40	0,730
87-107	10,7	7,70	1,095
107-131	9,5	7,00	1,095
131-170	10,9	9,10	0,876
4. Shumanay district Sh-1 Irrigated meadow-alluvial. Delta of Amudarya formed from layered alluvial deposits			
0-34	8,9	8,26	0,584
34-44	9,1	8,12	0,511
44-66	9,5	7,98	0,584
66-84	9,2	8,68	0,146
84-105	10,6	8,82	0,876
105-150	10,5	9,1	0,438

As a result of our research, we can see that the amount of carbonate fluctuated between 7% and 11% in both districts (Table 1). It was observed that the amount of carbonate is less in the upper layers of the sections, and it is washed downwards. It was found that it fluctuated between 7.6% and 10.7% in the old irrigated barren meadow soils. We can see that in our determined soils, CaCO_3 occupies the most part, that is, between 7.1% and 9.7%, and MgCO_3 fluctuates between 0.292% and 1.584%.

In newly irrigated meadow-alluvial soils, carbonate content varied from 8.9% to 10.9%, CaCO_3 content varied from 7.0% to 9.1%, and MgCO_3 from 0.146%. We can see that it fluctuated between 1.095%.

Conclusion: In the meadow-alluvial and takyrl-like meadow soils distributed on the right and left banks of the Lower Amudarya, the amount of carbonates is weakly carbonated, the mostly CaCO_3 is found, equal to 80-95% of the total amount. The remaining part is mainly MgCO_3 , which is found in soils in the form of dolomite.

Reference:

1. R.K. Kuziev and others. Guide to conducting soil surveys and drawing up soil maps for the maintenance of the state land cadastre. Tashkent, 2013. 52 p.
2. UzPITI. Agrochemical methods for studying soils and plants. Toshkent, 2007. 14-18 p.
3. E.V.Arinushkina. Guide to chemical analysis of soils. Moscow. 1977. -P. 277-310.

4. G.N.Kattayeva Genetic, ecological and reclamation properties of the dry bottom soil-soil bags of the Aral Sea (in the case of the western part) // diss abstract Tashkent-2024., p. 16.

